

Multi-Sensor Fusion for Edge-Based Motor Anomaly Detection on ESP32 Using an Autoencoder

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Abstract—Reliable condition monitoring of industrial motors requires the integration of multiple heterogeneous sensors. This paper presents a low-cost, edge-centric anomaly detection system built on the ESP32 microcontroller that fuses vibration (accelerometer/gyroscope), thermal (temperature), and rotational speed (Hall-effect) measurements. An unsupervised autoencoder model is trained to reconstruct normal sensor patterns, with deviations flagged using a threshold derived from training error statistics. Evaluated on a dataset of 2,280 multi-sensor samples, the proposed method identifies abnormal motor states with low computational cost, demonstrating the feasibility of sensor fusion and TinyML-style inference directly on ESP32 without cloud dependence.

Index Terms—Sensor fusion, Anomaly detection, Autoencoder, ESP32, Edge computing, Motor fault detection, Predictive maintenance, TinyML.

I. INTRODUCTION

Predictive maintenance in Industry 4.0 requires fast and reliable detection of departures from normal behaviour in rotating machinery. Rule-based alarms often miss gradual degradation or complex cross-channel patterns. Data-driven approaches learn structure in normal operation and are therefore well-suited for early detection of subtle anomalies. We target a practical constraint: running the detector entirely on a low-cost microcontroller to avoid cloud dependence, latency, and bandwidth.

This work demonstrates an end-to-end solution on the ESP32 that performs multi-sensor fusion (vibration, temperature, and RPM) and applies a compact autoencoder (AE) for unsupervised anomaly detection at the edge. The approach is simple enough for microcontroller deployment yet expressive enough to capture cross-sensor structure.

Contributions:

- A practical ESP32 hardware design integrating vibration, temperature, and RPM sensors for condition monitoring.
- A sensor-fusion autoencoder pipeline tailored to embedded constraints for unsupervised anomaly detection.

- A reproducible evaluation with publicly available artifacts (figures and CSV outputs).

II. BACKGROUND AND RELATED WORK

A. Anomaly Detection and Autoencoders

Anomaly detection aims to flag rare behaviour that departs from the distribution of normal operation. Classical methods include control charts and distance/density models; see [1] for a survey. Autoencoders (AEs) provide a learned, nonlinear alternative: training on normal data yields low reconstruction error on in-distribution inputs and higher error on anomalies. Linear AEs approximate PCA in the limit, while nonlinear AEs capture curved, low-dimensional manifolds [2], [3]. Recent reviews detail AE-based anomaly detection across domains, including industrial systems [4].

B. Edge/TinyML for Predictive Maintenance

Edge deployment reduces latency and bandwidth and avoids cloud dependence. The TinyML community has shown compact models running on microcontrollers with tight memory/compute budgets [5]. For rotating machinery, IoT pipelines for predictive maintenance using ML are well documented [6]–[8]. We add an end-to-end AE on ESP32, including model sizing and edge-side thresholding.

C. Sensor Fusion for Motors

Vibration, temperature, and RPM provide complementary views of motor health. Fusing these channels lets the model exploit cross-correlation structure and detect subtle deviations not obvious in any single stream. Standardizing features (zero mean, unit variance) prevents scale dominance and aligns the reconstruction loss with a likelihood interpretation. Recent studies in motor health monitoring emphasize the complementary role of heterogeneous sensors, where vibration data captures mechanical imbalance, temperature indicates thermal

Fig. 1. Wiring schematic for ESP32 with MPU6050 (vibration), DS18B20 (temperature), and A3144 (RPM via Hall effect).

stress, and RPM reflects load dynamics. Fusing these modalities improves robustness compared with single-sensor diagnostics, especially in resource-constrained platforms targeted by the IEEE Sensors community.

III. SYSTEM ARCHITECTURE AND HARDWARE

A. Sensors and Microcontroller

We integrate:

- **MPU6050**: 3-axis accelerometer/gyroscope for vibration;
- **DS18B20**: digital temperature sensor for thermal monitoring;
- **A3144**: Hall-effect sensor for RPM.

All sensors are interfaced to an ESP32-WROOM-32 for acquisition and processing.

B. Wiring and Power

Fig. 1 shows the complete wiring. The MPU6050 communicates via I²C (SDA/SCL). The DS18B20 uses a 1-Wire GPIO. The A3144 outputs a digital pulse signal proportional to rotation. Decoupling capacitors and pull-ups are included for signal quality.

IV. DATASET AND PREPROCESSING

The dataset contains 2,280 samples with nine numeric columns: *timestamp_us*, *ax_g*, *ay_g*, *az_g*, *gx_dps*, *gy_dps*, *gz_dps*, *temp_C*, *rpm*. Signals are standardized feature-wise to zero mean and unit variance using statistics computed on the training subset (first 60% of the sequence, assumed normal).

Fig. 2. Normalized sensor signals over time. Multiple channels are overlaid to visualize dynamics across vibration, temperature, and RPM.

Fig. 3. Feature correlation heatmap across numeric channels.

V. METHODOLOGY

A. Autoencoder

Let $\mathbf{x} \in \mathbb{R}^d$ denote a standardized feature vector ($d=9$). The AE learns $f_\theta : \mathbb{R}^d \rightarrow \mathbb{R}^d$ via a low-dimensional hidden layer to reconstruct normal inputs:

$$\hat{\mathbf{x}} = f_\theta(\mathbf{x}), \quad \mathcal{L}(\theta) = \|\mathbf{x} - \hat{\mathbf{x}}\|_2^2. \quad (1)$$

At inference, the per-sample reconstruction error $e = \|\mathbf{x} - \hat{\mathbf{x}}\|_2^2$ is compared against a threshold T computed from the training-error distribution:

$$T = \mu_e + \kappa\sigma_e, \quad (2)$$

with μ_e and σ_e the mean and standard deviation of training errors; we set $\kappa=1.5$.

B. Signal Model and Rationale

Assuming normal operating states lie near a low-dimensional manifold $\mathcal{M} \subset \mathbb{R}^d$, the AE reconstructs points near \mathcal{M} with low error, while off-manifold inputs (faults/transients) yield higher error. With standardized features, $e(\mathbf{x})$ approximates the negative log-likelihood under an

Fig. 4. Autoencoder reconstruction error (MSE) with threshold and detected anomalies.

isotropic Gaussian residual model, so thresholding e can be viewed as a likelihood-ratio test.

C. Threshold Selection and Calibration

Beyond the parametric rule above, two robust choices are practical: (i) *quantile* thresholding $T = Q_{1-\alpha}$ for a target false-alarm rate α ; and (ii) a *MAD*-based robust z-score $z_r = (e - \text{median}(e))/\text{MAD}(e)$ with a fixed cutoff (e.g., $|z_r| > 3.5$). For heavy-tailed residuals, a generalized Pareto fit to the upper tail stabilizes α across motors.

D. Edge Execution

The trained network is compact (single hidden layer, $2 \sim 16$ units depending on d) and suitable for embedded inference. Data acquisition runs in a periodic task; features are standardized using stored (μ, σ) , then passed to the network to obtain e ; an alert is issued if $e > T$.

E. Complexity and Feasibility on ESP32

For an AE with d inputs and h hidden units, the parameter count is $2dh + h + d$ (two weight matrices plus biases). With $d=9$ and $h \in [2, 16]$, this is $\mathcal{O}(10^2)$ parameters ($\ll 1$ kB in 32-bit floats). A forward pass requires roughly $2dh$ multiply-accumulate operations plus activations, well below a millisecond at typical ESP32 clock rates. Stored standardization statistics $(\mu, \sigma) \in \mathbb{R}^{2d}$ are negligible. These budgets comfortably fit microcontroller constraints, leaving headroom for acquisition and alerting.

VI. RESULTS

A. Quantitative Summary

Using the first 60% of sequential samples as “normal” for training, we compute reconstruction MSE on the full set. For this dataset the fitted threshold yields $T \approx 3.9641$, with **2** samples exceeding T (flagged as anomalies) out of **2,280** total. The flagged points show coincident perturbations in vibration and RPM, consistent with imbalance or transient loading [8].

Fig. 5. Distribution of reconstruction errors; the dashed line indicates the decision threshold.

Fig. 6. An example anomaly plot from a prior run (reference visualization).

B. Operating Point Sensitivity

The operating point is governed by κ (or equivalently the target false-alarm rate α). Increasing κ reduces false positives but risks missing incipient faults; decreasing κ does the opposite. The current setting flags 2/2,280 samples as anomalies.

C. Robustness Checks

To mitigate drift and sensor bias, we recommend: (i) re-estimating (μ, σ) and T on rolling windows; (ii) smoothing e_t with a short moving average to suppress spikes; and (iii) appending domain features (RMS vibration over N -sample frames, band-limited spectral energy) to the nine raw channels to improve separability with minimal compute overhead.

D. Sensor Contribution

Each sensing modality contributes differently to fault detection: vibration features highlight imbalance or misalignment, temperature reflects thermal overload, and RPM variations capture load transients. Their fusion within the autoencoder framework ensures anomalies are detected even when a single channel shows weak deviation, demonstrating the benefit of multi-sensor integration on low-cost embedded hardware.

VII. DISCUSSION

The proposed AE operationalizes a simple statistical test at the edge: learn a compact normality model from fused,

standardized streams, and flag deviations by thresholding reconstruction error. Compared with fixed-rule alarms, this captures cross-channel structure and gradual drift. Compared with heavier sequence models, the compact feed-forward AE provides orders-of-magnitude lower latency and memory on microcontrollers, aligning with TinyML best practices [5]. Practical deployment requires per-motor calibration of T , periodic refresh of standardization statistics, and conservative alerting (e.g., requiring K consecutive exceedances) in noisy settings.

Limitations: Our unsupervised setting treats the first 60% as normal and lacks labeled faults, so classical precision/recall cannot be reported. Future work includes collecting labeled fault modes (imbalance, misalignment, bearing wear), benchmarking against one-class baselines and small sequence models, and exploring quantized inference to further reduce memory and energy.

VIII. CONCLUSION AND FUTURE WORK

We presented an end-to-end, edge-based anomaly detection system for motors using ESP32 and an autoencoder trained on normal behavior. On a 2,280-sample dataset with 9 channels, simple thresholding of reconstruction error yielded actionable flags with minimal compute. Future directions include TinyML-specific optimizations, adaptive thresholds, spectral features for vibration, and long-horizon evaluation on diverse motors. This work demonstrates that sensor-fusion based anomaly detection can be realized on a low-cost ESP32, enabling practical, embedded predictive maintenance without reliance on the cloud.

ARTIFACTS AND REPRODUCIBILITY

All figures referenced in this paper are included alongside the \LaTeX source. Machine-readable outputs for reproducibility are provided: `dataset_summary.csv` (feature statistics) and `autoencoder_results.csv` (per-sample MSE and anomaly flags).

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